

Current State and Trends of Digital and Media Advertising Effectiveness in Uzbekistan

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Abstract: Today, digital technologies are increasingly penetrating into all aspects of life, which, in turn, makes digitization an urgent task on the agenda. Based on this, this article analyzes trends in the world and Uzbekistan regarding the creation of digital advertising.

Keywords: digital economy, digital technologies, commercial platform, marketing, digital marketing, media marketing.

INTRODUCTION

The current digitization process is creating new opportunities and peaks in the field of marketing and advertising. Today, digital and media advertising activities have become an important tool for businesses and organizations to establish effective relationships with customers. The increase in the number of Internet users, the widespread use of social networks and mobile devices has made digital advertising one of the main channels for reaching consumers. These trends are also reflected in Uzbekistan. Due to the development of digital infrastructure in the country and the increase in the number of internet users, the field of digital and media advertising is growing significantly. Businesses and entrepreneurs are using various digital advertising tools in order to improve customer relations and increase competitiveness in the market.

Digitization of the economy primarily involves increasing the efficiency and competitiveness of the economy. The results of the World Bank's research entitled "Digital Dividends" show how relevant and important the digital economy is in the development of countries' economies. In particular, a 10 percent increase in internet speed leads to an increase in the country's GDP. In developed countries, this figure is 1.21 percent, while in developing countries it is 1.38 percent. So, if the Internet speed increases by 2 times, it is possible to achieve an increase in GDP by almost 15%. In addition, according to experts' calculations, due to digitalization, the costs of product production and service will decrease by 10-40%, the idleness of equipment by 30-50%, the costs of bringing products and services to the market by 20-50%, and the costs of improving product quality and advertising by 10- Up to 20%, and costs of storage of production stocks are reduced by 20-50%. Today, digital technologies are rapidly entering the field of marketing of goods and services. One such tool is social media marketing.

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SUBJECT

The topic of media marketing has been thoroughly studied by Western economists M. Kotler in his book "Marketing 4.0" marketing in the digital space researched application issues.

Among local economists, Ghulomov S.S.[2], Begalov B.A.[3], Bekmurodov A.Sh., Musaliev A.A.[4], etc. studies were conducted on the prospects.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

As in all fields in the world, the role of digital technologies in the field of marketing is increasing. Currently, the number of active users of the Internet, especially social networks, is increasing every year in Uzbekistan. For comparison, at the end of 2021, there were 27.2 million Internet users and 25.3 million mobile subscribers in the country, and by now the number of Internet users in Uzbekistan is more than 31 million people, which is +13.97% more than in 2021. means The number of users of mobile devices is about 30 million.

Promotion in some social networks has a positive effect on advertising in search engines, this is especially true if the social network platform and the search engine belong to the same company . Social networks have become not only a new space for communication, but also a place for self-expression, work, shopping, finding the necessary information and people.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSIONS

The advertising market in the country is growing by 20-25% every year. Last year, its volume reached 709.2 billion soums (\$2021 million at the average annual rate of 66.9 years) — that is 2 times more than three years ago.

In 2021, the share of digital advertising in the total structure of the market was 18%, which was 16% in 2020, and 15% in 2019, respectively. In terms of value, the volume of digital advertising grew by 32% last year, or from 82.2 billion soums to 108.2 billion soums (Figure 1).

This growth is also related to general "digitization": more and more advertisers are switching to online platforms to attract younger audiences.

1 . The share of digital advertising in the total advertising market, billion soums

In addition, the focus on online advertising is explained by the financial difficulties of advertising on television. According to research by Kantar, the average TV viewing time is 2.5 hours per day, and TV inflation for advertisers reaches 20-50%. The rate of inflation on the Internet is significantly lower - 5-7%.

Despite the fact that Internet traffic is expensive, the number of permanent smartphone users is increasing in the digital sphere of Uzbekistan. According to a Hootsuite report, up to 75% of traffic in the country comes from phones.

The most popular social network in Uzbekistan is YouTube, which has 5.7 million users, and the main audience is people aged 25 to 34 (36%). It is noteworthy that only about 300 channel creators have chosen Uzbekistan as their country, so the domestic market is not yet developed enough. Foreign companies that are now entering the market and actively engaged in content marketing can help with growth.

The country has a platform Mover.uz, which is an alternative to YouTube.

2 - picture. Number of social network users, thousand people

Telegram is the most popular messenger. As of February 1, 2022, 18 million people have used it. Instagram is the fastest growing social network: its audience has grown by 212% over the past four years.

Odnoklassniki is more popular in Uzbekistan than in other CIS countries: 16.7 million people are registered on the social network. The audience of social networks is people between the ages of 25 and 34 (about 42%), the 35-44 age group makes up 30% of the total number of users.

The media market of Uzbekistan, which has the largest population in the Central Asian region, is attracting interest from investors who are opening new private TV channels and online media. However, in the last 20 years, there have been no large-scale studies of the media market in Uzbekistan, only local and segmented studies of various media groups. Thus, according to Ledokol Group research, the media market of Uzbekistan shows moderate growth. In 2021, advertising prices increased by 13%, while net market growth was 12%.

A large part of the media market is occupied by television, which accounts for almost 2/3 of the entire media budget. in the next 3 years, between 2017 and 2021, the share of the Internet

in the total budget increased from 3 percent to 19 percent. Radio remains the most stable segment of the media market. Today, more than 35 radio stations are operating in Uzbekistan. Its market share is 2%.

Television of Uzbekistan consists of local private and state channels of MTRK, as well as foreign cable TV channels. Nineteen of the existing 74 TV channels and 37 of the 7 radio stations were broadcast nationwide, and the remaining 55 TV channels and 30 radio stations were broadcast at the regional level. At the same time, 36 of them are state TV channels and 38 are private, the number of state broadcasting radio channels has been reduced to 5, and the remaining 32 are private.

In November 2018, Uzbekistan switched to placing television ads based on television ratings, which made it possible to place ads based on the popularity of shows instead of buying airtime. In the last three years, since the introduction of rated television viewing, the flow of investment has increased. Since 2021, the television advertising market is recovering after the quarantine, so the growth of advertisers' investments is 2%. In 2021, the share of the television market of Uzbekistan is one of the largest in the world. The number of advertisers, including foreign advertisers, is increasing every year.

Despite the fact that the media market of Uzbekistan is developing quite rapidly, it still occupies a rather modest place in the country's economy compared to developed countries where the media sector gathers large resources.

CONCLUSION

It is impossible to organize a general, universal scheme for organizing work on the basis of modern marketing principles in the international market. network characteristics, organizational structure, type of activity of light industry indicate the need to choose a special model of marketing in each specific case.

The effective implementation of the use of the modern marketing type system provides for the existence of various forms of private property and the expansion of the activities of commercial units.

In order to improve the quality of personnel being trained in the field of digital marketing and media marketing, it is necessary to increase the practicality of educational programs and educational materials of higher educational institutions, and for this, it is necessary to develop cooperation between higher educational institutions and companies operating in the field.

LIST OF REFERENCES

Books

1. Gulyamov SS and others. Blockchain technologies in the digital economy. T.: Economy-Finance, 2019. 396 p.
2. Begalov B.A., Analysis of user demand in evaluating the quality of information systems being created for small business entities. Scientific electronic magazine "Economy and innovative technologies". No. 1, January-February, 2015
3. Bobojonov A.B. Methodological aspects of development of business of information products and services in Uzbekistan.: Ph.D. dis. iqt. science. - Tashkent: TDIU, 2018, - 155 pages.

Magazines

1. Butkovskaya, G.V. and Statkus, A.V., 2019. Digital marketing: povedenie potrebiteley. Vestnik University, (5).
2. Chaffey D. Digital marketing. Pearson UK; 2019 Feb 5.

3. Vassileva, B., 2017. Marketing 4.0: How technologies transform marketing organization. Óbuda University e-Bulletin, 7(1), p.47.
4. Viana, NA (2016). Digital wine marketing: Social media marketing for the wine industry. In BIO Web of Conferences (Vol. 7, p. 03011). EDP Sciences.

Website

<https://www.spot.uz/ru/2022/09/22/wunder-digital/>

<https://ru.eureporter.co/world/uzbekistan/2022/10/18/uzbekistans-media-sector-in-development-reforms-contribute-to-the-inflow-of-private-investment/>